

Cuida-AI: Virtual Assistant for Optimizing Oncology Care in Public Hospitals in Recife – Brazil

Focus Group Script:

Section 1: Process Information

- How are patients referred to the institution (e.g., public healthcare system, private insurance, or self-pay)?
- What are the biggest challenges you face when seeking information about treatments, medications, or guidance within the hospital?

Section 2: Proposal Validation

- What do you expect from a virtual assistant that helps with hospital services?
- What types of information or services would you like the virtual assistant to provide?
- In what situations would you most feel the need for support or find a virtual assistant particularly useful?
- Is there anything else you would like to share about Cuida-AI or ways to improve hospital care for cancer patients?